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Nonnegative matrix factorization for source separation of monophonic audio sources

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Introduction

The process with which we extract separate 'pieces'/parts' of a signal, which is a mixture of these parts, by means of computer programs is called Source Separation. The types of signals used for Source Separation varies with few examples being audio, medical, neural (used in the research of brain function understanding), economical, radio, image, video signals.

The first references regarding Source Separation exist in papers dating back in the '80s [1] [9] and for the first time the formulation of the problem in a statistical frame took place in 1985 from Herault and Jutten [10]. The theoretical study and practical application of source separation was increased considerably with the application of ICA (Independent Component Analysis) in the beginning of the '90s [6]. In the case of audio signals, several psychoacoustic studies, such as Bregman's [4] provided the basis for algorithms which mimicked human auditory perception. These developments brought two different approaches for source separation, the statistical/mathematical and one inspired from the human auditory perception system. One example for the latter approach is the way a human separates the voice of his interlocutor from intense surrounding noise or/ and other peoples voices, a problem often referred a *the cocktail party effect*. The algorithms that attempt to emulate such behavior are not (yet) comparable to human perception.

The difficulty of a source separation problem is mostly determined by two factors; the mixes' nature and the amount of prior information we have about the sources (or the mix). Source separation is called *blind* if there is little to no information about the mix. This kind of source separation is called *blind source separation*. In reality a minimum probabilistic assumption that has to do with the statistical independence or sparse representation or (as will be examined in this thesis) the non-negativity of the sources always occurs.

The development of Machine Learning theory, data mining and pattern recognition and the simultaneous increase in computational power of modern computers have laid the tracks for new applications in musical audio signals, such as the

possibility of recognition of content and its proper management. In spite of all the recent success, the source separation process is a tough challenge and it will take a lot of work for the algorithms' performance to become useful in daily life.

0.1 Definition of the Problem

When two or more ($y_m(n)$) sound waves coincide in a specific point in space and in a particular point in time, the instantaneous amplitude of the produced wave ($x(n)$) is given by the sum of the instantaneous amplitudes of the initial waves, according to the principle of superposition. Mathematically this is written:

$$x(n) = \sum_{m=1}^M y_m(n) \quad , \quad n = 1, \dots, N \quad (1)$$

where y_m is the m^{th} source-signal in time n , and M is the number of source-signals.

Audio Source Separation is defined as the process of recovering one or more source-signals $y_m(n)$ from $x(n)$. It is important to mention that there is a significant difference between the initial source that is required to be recovered and the point that the initial mix took place. While the signal mixing occurs after an acoustical signal has been converted to electrical signal where all individual sources are summed, through source separation, sources are sought to be recovered at their point of initial creation. A complication in this described model is that the mentioned definition of the source-signal is not unique. More specifically, the model analyzed was used as prior knowledge for the sources.

0.2 Representations of the Acoustical Signal

It is important to introduce here an introductory description of the two basic ways with which the input signal is represented, with the first one being the way the signal is captured and the second the way the signal is viewed by the algorithm, transformed into the frequency domain.

0.2a Representation in the time domain

The most common representation of an acoustical signal is through its sampled waveform, where each signal describes an intensity of sound pressure at a given point in time. Even though this representation allows for a lot of basic applications of signal processing, it is not directly useful for the perceptually harder ones, such as source

separation. For this reason, this representation is called intermediate, because it is transformed to provide the signal in another form, which will contain more useful information.

Figure 1: representation in the time domain

Figure 2: zoom in of fig. 1

0.2b Representation in the frequency-time domain

The signal is split into smaller "windows" (frames) (typically 10-100 milliseconds in audio applications) and the Fourier transform is applied to each window. This transformation of a window into frequency is called spectra. The term spectrogram is used to refer to the set of all spectra, where the time position of the windows determine the axis of time.

Figure 3: Representation in the frequency-time domain

A lot of important aspects of a sound are determined by its spectra [8]. It is also known that the human auditory system can perform frequency analysis of some

sort [16].

0.3 Applications on Acoustical Signals

As has been determined in [3] when it is necessary to retain the maximum amount of quality then the problem is *Audio Quality Oriented* with examples being unmixing, remixing and compression of acoustical signals, while when information about the content is required, the the problem is *Significance Oriented*, we are interested in separation in a level that allows us understanding, musical transcription belongs to this kind of problem as well as *Music Information Retrieval*. One more way of "discretizing" types of source separation is *separation for understanding* as it happens in the case of Music Information Retrieval an *separation without Understanding* as it happens in the case of unmixing.

0.3a Compression of Acoustical Signals

Modern methods of compressing acoustical signals, such as MP3 or AAC, quantize the signal up to the point that it is not easily perceptible from the human auditory system. A new way of addressing acoustical signal compression is based on the, still experimental, "*Object-based Audio Coding*". During *Object-based Audio Coding* the signal is separated into "sound objects", which have some common characteristics, such as the same amplitude and/ or the common activated frequency (where basically spectral modeling of the signal takes place. Next, only these objects are transmitted (or stored) and finally, with the use of a decoder, an approximation of the original signal is recovered. A more specific process would be modeling of each specific musical organ separately and the transmission of only these models (and their activation times) but this in reality required their initial separation and subsequently modeling each one.

0.3b Unmixing and Remixing

An application of source separation relevant to unmixing has to do with the removal of unwanted sources. With immediate examples stemming from separating the voice from a musical piece for Karaoke purposes or, more generally, removal of musical instrument from a musical piece in order to help a practicing musician, restoration of musical signals from old recordings or denoising of input signals to help improve the use of hearing aides.

One more demanding application from the rest is the complete separation of the initial mix into source signals with a purpose of being heard. In the case of musical signals this means recovering a multi-track recording from a monophonic or stereophonic mix. In the ideal case, the output signals of the algorithm should have similar quality as they had when recorded before the mixing process. Unfortunately, this kind of process is, in general terms, yet impossible.

One more application with a huge practical interest is remixing of an initial mix, with the retrieval of a set of separated signals, they can be mixed again allowing different and more extensive processing on the sources, something impossible in the case where all the signals are summed. This process is less demanding from complete separation as when remixing the sources, imperfections coming from the separation can be hidden. Some examples of remixing involve upmixing recordings from monophonic to stereophonic [15], from stereophonic to surround [2], the production of a musical signal when initial sources don't exist [19] and also its use as a creative tool for new compositions.

0.3c Music Information Retrieval and Transcription

In music information retrieval and musical transcription the target output is information content. In most cases it is easier to analyze partially separated signals as far as rhythm, frequency structure than analyzing the initial musical signal. Some applications in music content and information retrieval is the recognition and categorization in genre (whether it is Jazz, Western classical or Hindu classical), composer recognition [13], search through similarity of recognition of a musical piece. An application that uses both source separation and the aforementioned applications is the extraction of a general conclusion after an analysis of the separated signals. On the other side, Musical signal analysis techniques could be used to achieve (are in difficult cases even allow) separation.

Transcription of polyphonic musical signals is an equally (if not more) difficult problem. There exist successful methods for tone recognition and transcription of monophonic instruments or melodies [11], and there are results in the right direction for two or three voices, but when the number of voices is increased the problem remains unsolved, until today. Problems are the same as in source separation, when a lot of instruments are playing in the same frequency they are detected as one instrument, a problem that repeats itself with time activations, overlaps in rhythmically casual music, force the algorithms to recognize them again as one instrument. Attempts have been made in this field, without the use of source separation, [14],

something that could be used and to create successful transcriptions on each separated signal. Again, inverting the perspective, the existence of a musical transcription prior to separation, could aid in a lot better source separation.

0.4 Summary

This thesis will focus on source separation, and more specifically on monophonic audio signals consisting of percussive sources with methods we will analyze in the second chapter.

In the first, introductory chapter, we defined the problem of Source Separation of Audio Signals, the way the signals are represented, we referenced the application and a possible grouping by their type and a first comparison of source separation methods.

In the second chapter there will be a brief analysis of the history and theory around nonnegative matrix factorization, Bregman divergences and a justification for selecting Itakura-Saito and the Majorization-Minimization algorithm we will use for the method.

In the third chapter we will present measurements for source separation performed by the extracted algorithm for signals consisting of percussive sources.

In the fourth chapter conclusions will be extracted from the results of the third chapter, the effectiveness and quality of the algorithm will be evaluated and possible future research direction will be examined.

Part I

Theory & Algorithm

Chapter 1

Theory

1.1 Introduction

In this chapter we will present the theory and the logic behind nonnegative matrix factorization, objective cost functions of the Bregman family of divergences and its subclass, the β divergence, and the reasons behind the choice of the Itakura-Saito as the objective function, as well as a basic description of the logic involving the construction of MM algorithms.

1.2 Representations of the acoustical signal - Part B

The representation in time (as shown in fig 1) is the way the acoustical signal is sampled. The speed of sampling is called the sampling frequency f_s , as a consequence and while the human ear is not capable of comprehending frequencies above $\sim 20.000\text{Hz}$ and according to the Sampling Theorem, in the present thesis the sampling frequency we will use will be equal to 44.100Hz , which equivalently means sampling the sound pressure every $T = 0,000023$ seconds. This type of sampling frequency involves a very large amount of samples for relatively small periods of time, for example for 3 minutes of a sampled acoustical signal $44100\text{Hz} \times 180 \text{ seconds} \approx 8$ million samples are collected. The value of every sample corresponds to the amount of oscillation of the analog acoustical signal at the exact moment of conception.

The transform used for the conversion of the samples from the time domain to the frequency domain, is the discrete form of the Fourier transform (DFT), which is widely used because of its easy calculation through the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The Discrete Fourier Transform takes as its input a sequence of samples, decomposes it as a sum of sines and cosines, each with its respective amount of

existing energy, as given by the formula below.

$$X(\omega_k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]e^{-i\omega_k t_n} \quad , \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (1.1)$$

where

$$\omega_k = 2\pi \frac{k}{N} f_s \quad , \quad f_s = \frac{1}{T} \quad , \quad t_n = nT$$

We call X the spectrum x , $X(\omega)$ is the k -th sample of the spectrum at frequency ω_k , f_s is the sampling frequency with period T . As a consequence the formula becomes;

$$X(\omega_k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n]e^{-i\frac{2\pi kn}{N}} \quad , \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (1.2)$$

According to Euler's formula $e^{-i\omega_k t_n} = \cos(\omega_k t_n) - i \sin(\omega_k t_n)$, the decomposition as a sum of sines and cosines:

$$X(\omega_k) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n](\cos(\omega_k t_n) - i \sin(\omega_k t_n)) \quad , \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, N-1 \quad (1.3)$$

The spectrum is Hermitian if the values of the sequence of samples are real, if $f(-x) = \overline{f(x)}$. Because of this symmetry, we can ignore the spectra samples with negative values and recreate them again from the positive spectrum samples. Simplifying the scales, the calculations done on spectra are done from 0Hz $\omega_s f_s/2$ Hz. DFT is defined only for frequencies $\omega_k = 2\pi k f_s/N$, equally distributing the continuum of frequencies in k distinct points, the frequency bins. For example, if the size of the input to the DFT is 512 samples, only 257 can be used because of symmetry, which will quantize the signal into 257 frequency bins. The amount of energy that has 'fallen' between two frequency bins is distributed among those two frequency bins, depending on its distance from each one. The Power spectrum, $|X(\omega_k)|^2$, corresponds to the total energy contained in each frequency bin. This even separation of frequencies, is contrary to the way the human auditory system perceives frequencies, frequently 1 important frequency exists in 2 frequency bins, a problem partially bypassed by increasing the input samples to the DFT.

One more characteristic of the Discrete Fourier Transform it returns the energy of any frequency contained in the input sample sequence, when the period of these frequencies is smaller than the size of the sequence, independent of time length. This occurs because the Fourier Transform contains no time relevant information. In 1964 Dennis Gabor dealt with this problem when, for the first time, he used a technique called Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). In this technique, the signal

Figure 1.1: Window Types

is divided in smaller parts (usually referred to as windows) then, every window is multiplied by a function of time ($w(n)$) and, lastly, the Fourier Transform is applied to these windows. With this technique, D. Gabor managed to approximate the initial signal with a much better accuracy, Some types of windows are show in fig 1.1.

The size of the windows is of particular importance, because larger windows (comprised of 4096-8192 samples) are necessary in order to fit lower frequencies (with larger periods), while smaller window sizes (comprised of 512-2048 samples) are required because they preserve more accurate temporal characteristics of the initial signal. The exchange between existence of information in the temporal or frequency characteristics of the initial signal exists in every time-frequency transform and is something related to the uncertainty principle in signal analysis.

From the figure 1.2 it instantly becomes clear that the sum of any type of windows besides the parallelogram ones -whose sample value is 1 at every point- cannot return the initial signal unless one more step is introduced, overlap. According to which, each window covers a percentage (or a number of samples) of its previous one. This percentage usually ranges around 50%, but for better temporal accuracy it could reach up to a sample less than the overall window size, some examples on fig. 1.3.

On all measurements on this thesis the window with the sinusoidal time function

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Figure 1.2: Window Addition

Figure 1.3: 3 STFTs on the same signal. (from left to right) The first one has the same size as the signal, 5001 samples, the second one 2048 samples with an overlap of 2047 samples and the third one 512 samples with 511 samples of overlap.

will be used.

1.3 Matrix Factorization

1.3a Matrix Factorization

Matrix factorization has a common course in Numerical Linear Algebra and Applied Statistics / Psychometrics [12] as it offers a way of simplifying an initial problem by offering a speedup in solving it as well as understanding "hidden" information within the initial matrix.

From the Numerical Linear Algebra perspective, matrix factorization is generally used as a means to solve a difficult problem with more ease, an example would be the factorization $A = L \cdot U$ in the attempt to solve $A \cdot x = b$, where L and U are triangular matrices and by solving the (easier) $L \cdot y = b$ and $U \cdot y = x$ we can find the unknown x . In this framework, the information contained in the factors L and U is not important. This is not the case when factorization is used in the field of Applied Statistics, where the information contained in the factors is of critical importance.

It is usual in Applied Statistics/Psychometric that the initial matrix $A^{n \times p}$ is a set of observations of n objects and p variables. The purpose of matrix factorization from this perspective, is the acquisition of a matrix of smaller dimensions (and thus simplified observations) which will approximate the initial (A) allowing better understanding of its structure. More specifically, in Psychometrics (where a lot of research in matrix factorization began) Factor Analysis is used with success with the purpose being the 'creation' of a summary from a large number of variables (observed answers in a series of questions) in order to help understand a property or characteristic of the surveyed people.

It is worth mentioning that besides the expectations of N.L.A. and A.S./P. are completely different, both aim at the same thing; simplifying the initial problem.

Success of matrix factorization in the fact that there exists some indirect or latent information that is revealed in the factor, has raised an interest for research in other scientific disciplines and, as referenced in [17], some important problems on which matrix factorization is useful are;

Lossy Compression: where a lower dimensional representation of the signal as a more compact way of representing it which contains the most important information of the initial higher-dimensional representation input. Use of these compressed signals can reduce the computational cost when it (exponentially) scales up with each dimension.

Signal Compression : Reduced representation corresponds to some 'hidden' signal or process which is indirectly observed. One example being the previous one on Psychometrics and one more being the analysis of Gene Expression where the target is the reconstruction of cellular processes and conditions based on observed levels of gene expression.

Prediction : In the case that the initial matrix has been partially observed, matrix factorization can be used in order to predict the unobserved parts of the initial matrix.

Structure Recognition : Matrix factorization is usually used in the framework of non-supervised learning in order to model structure. Every object in a body of words/ images corresponds to a row on the matrix and the columns correspond to the characteristics of the objects (appearance) of words/ color levels of every pixel. At this point matrix factorization can be used in order to understand the relationship among the objects in the body and basic ways of their variance.

The methods used to factorize from the perspective of feature/ information extraction from an initial matrix or data, essentially differ as far as the constraints imposed on it and on the way error is measured between the approximations and the initial matrix.

1.3b Nonnegative matrix Factorization

Nonnegative Matrix Factorization targets to approximate an initial matrix with a product of two others.

$$V \approx W \cdot H \tag{1.4}$$

όπου :

$$V \in \mathfrak{R}^{F \times N}, W \in \mathfrak{R}^{F \times K}, H \in \mathfrak{R}^{K \times N}$$

Separating the initial matrix in K factors. Because it constitutes only an approximation and not a full representation, in the literature it is also referred as Nonnegative Matrix Approximation. Since, what is of interest to us is dimensionality reduction of the initial matrix, K is usually selected as $(F + N)K < FN$.

The only constraint imposed in this factorization is that the information contained in V , W and H ¹ to be nonnegative. We impose;

$$V \in \mathfrak{R}^{\geq 0, F \times N}, W \in \mathfrak{R}^{\geq 0, F \times K} \text{ και } H \in \mathfrak{R}^{\geq 0, K \times N}$$

¹as shorthand we will use the approximation of V with $\hat{V} = W \cdot H$

A consequence of this constraint is non existence of deductions, while V is simply the product of matrices. So factors W and H contain basic parts of the initial matrix, something that is consistent with the human perception that everything is a set of the parts that compose it. In the literature factors W and H are described as followed;

W : the basis, the dictionary, the explanatory variables, the patterns

H : the activation coefficients, expansion coefficients

W is learned from the set $V = [V_1 \dots V_N]$ while the nonnegativity of W ensures the proper & essential translation of the dictionary, since w_k and the initial matrix v_n belong to the same space. As far as sound is concerned, the columns of W are the k points of an FFT. While H produces the representation of parts of objects since deductions are not allowed.

1.3c Comparison with other methods

Comparing NMF with two other methods, Vector Quantization (VQ) and Principle Component Analysis (PCA) we will be able to see how more intuitive and simple are the produced factors.

In the VQ method the constraint on the factors are that every column of H is a unary vector, with one element equal to one and every other equal to zero. This leads to the approximation of the initial matrix composed of one element of H and one element of W .

In the PCA method the constraints on the factors are, firstly the columns of W must be orthocanonical and, secondly, rows of H should be orthogonal with each other. These constraints allow a distributed representation in which every approximation of every initial element be a linear combination of various elements of H and W .

Differences of these methods are clearly shown on the next figure, separation through NMF gives a basis from parts of 2, while through VQ the basis is practically on a 1 – 1 correspondence with the initial and through the PCA methods, there exists again a separation by parts, but, because negative values are allowed (and the red color corresponds to negative values) the basis created contains more complex parts.

1.3d Application

More specifically in this thesis the nonnegative matrix V will be the matrix of the power spectrum of an acoustical signal $x[n]$ which will be approximated from two

Figure 1.4: Comparison NMF, VQ, PCA

Figure 1.5: Nonnegative Matrix Factorization on a Power Spectrum

matrices W and H , where W will contain the spectral profiles and H will contain the activation times. Of course this is an arbitrary way of calling both, as the transform is valid for $V^T = H^T W^T$.

1.4 Objective Function

Factorization (1.4) is usually sought after the minimization problem of :

$$\min_{W,H} D(V|WH) \quad (1.5)$$

with the elements of $W, H \geq 0$. $D(V|WH)$ is a way of measuring similarity of V with its approximation, \hat{V} , such that :

$$D(V|WH) = \sum_{f=1}^F \sum_{n=1}^N d([V]_{fn} | [WH]_{fn}) \quad (1.6)$$

where $d(x|y)$ is a scalar positive function in respect to $y \in \mathfrak{R}_+$ given $x \in \mathfrak{R}_+$, an objective function, with only one minimum, zero, when $x = y$.

1.4a Bregman Divergence

A class of cost functions widely used in optimization and clustering problems is the Bregman divergence which is defined as followed:

Definition 1.4.1 Given a function $\phi(x) : \mathfrak{R}_n \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ strictly convex and differentiable, then the Bregman divergence is defined as followed :

$$D\phi(x||y) = \phi(x) - \phi(y) - (x-y)^T \nabla \phi(y) \quad (1.7)$$

where $\nabla\phi(y)$ is the derivative of ϕ in y .

Some of the most basic properties of the Bregman divergence are:

- (i) **Convexity** : The Bregman divergence $D\phi(x||y)$ is always convex with respect to p , but often is not with respect to q .
- (ii) **Nonnegativity** : Bregman divergence is nonnegative, $D\phi(x||y) \geq 0$ and is zero when $p = q$
- (iii) **Linearity** : Every positive linear combination of Bregman divergences is a Bregman divergence.

$$D_{c_1\phi_1+c_2\phi_2}(x||y) = c_1D_{\phi_1}(x||y) + c_2D_{\phi_2}(x||y) \quad (1.8)$$

where c_1, c_2 positive constants, ϕ_1, ϕ_2 strictly convex functions.

- (iv) **The property of the three points, generalizes the law of Cosines** :

$$D_\phi(x||y) = D_\phi(x||z) + D_\phi(z||y) - (x-z)^T \frac{\delta}{\delta y} \phi(y) - \frac{\delta}{\delta z} \phi(z) \quad (1.9)$$

Bregman divergence is not a real metric, because the triangular inequality does not hold. This is a property that holds and on the β -divergence.

As an example, for $\phi(x) = \frac{x^2}{2}$ Bregman divergence becomes the squared euclidean distance:

$$D_2(x||y) = \frac{1}{2} \|x - y\|_2^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i (x_i - y_i)^2 \quad (1.10)$$

1.4b β -divergencies

A useful cost function for musical signal processing, is the family of β -divergences, which is a parametrized cost function with only one parameter, β , which has as special cases the euclidean distance for $\beta = 2$, Kullback-Liebler for $\beta = 1$ as well as the Itakura Saito divergence for $\beta = 0$. We have to mention again that family of β -divergences is not a real metric, because the triangular inequality does not hold.

Definition 1.4.2

$$d_\beta(x||y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\beta(\beta-1)}(x^\beta + (\beta-1) - \beta xy^{\beta-1}) & \beta \in \mathbb{R} - 0, 1 \\ x \log \frac{x}{y} - x - y & \beta = 1 \\ \frac{x}{y} - \log \frac{x}{y} - 1 & \beta = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1.11)$$

Figure 1.6: Squared Euclidean Distance

Figure 1.7: Kullback-Liebler Divergence (Relative Entropy)

The first and second derivative of $d_\beta(x|y)$ with respect to y are continuous on β and are :

$$d'_\beta(x|y) = y^{\beta-2}(y-x) \quad (1.12)$$

$$d''_\beta(x|y) = y^{\beta-3}[(\beta-1)y - (\beta-2x)] \quad (1.13)$$

The derivative shows that $d_\beta(x|y)$, as a function of y , has a unique minimum when $x = y$ and it increases for $|y - x|$ justifying its relevance as a measure of distance. The second derivative shows that β -divergence is convex when $\beta \in [1, 2]$. Outside this interval the divergence can be expressed as a sum of one convex, concave and a constant part, such that :

$$d_\beta(x|y) = \check{d}_\beta(x|y) + \hat{d}(x|y) + \bar{d}_\beta(x) \quad (1.14)$$

where $\check{d}_\beta(x|y)$ is convex, $\hat{d}(x|y)$ concave and $\bar{d}_\beta(x)$ constant function with respect to y .

One remarkable property of β -divergence is scale invariance :

$$d_\beta(\lambda x|\lambda y) = \lambda^\beta d_\beta(x|y) \quad (1.15)$$

This property implies that factorizations obtained with $\beta > 0$ (for example with $\beta = 1$) 'pay more attention' to elements with higher values and carry the consequence that their approximation is less accurate for elements with low energy and, inversely, factorizations with $\beta < 0$ 'pay more attention' to elements with lower values. It has been shown that factorization based on the absolute spectra with $\beta = .5$ brings the best results for musical transcription.

Figure 1.8: β -divergences

1.4c Itakura-Saito

Itakura-Saito divergence

$$d_{IS} = \frac{x}{y} - \log \frac{x}{y} - 1 \quad (1.16)$$

initial came up as the Maximum Likelihood Estimator of speech spectra. It was used as a measure of similarity of two spectra and is often used as the typical similarity measure in the speech processing community because of the very intuitive reconstructed signals it produces as a minimization problem.

Itakura-Saito can also occur from the Bregman divergence for $\phi(y) = -\log y$, something more clearly shown in the next example:

If $F(e^{j\theta})$ is the power spectra of a signal $f(t)$, then $\phi(F) = -2\pi - \pi \cdot \int \log(F(e^{j\theta})) d\theta$ is convex in F and correspond to the rhythm of the negative entropy of the signal, with the presupposition it was created from a Static Gaussian Process (Palus, 1997;

Figure 1.9: Itakura-Saito Divergence

Cover and Thomas, 1991). Bregman divergence between $F(e^{j\theta})$ and $G(e^{j\theta})$ (of the power spectrum of another signal) is given from:

$$d_\phi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \left(-\log(F(e^{j\theta})) + \log(G(e^{j\theta})) - (F(e^{j\theta}) - G(e^{j\theta})) \left(-\frac{1}{G(e^{j\theta})} \right) \right) d\theta$$

$$d_\phi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \left(-\log\left(\frac{F(e^{j\theta})}{G(e^{j\theta})}\right) + \frac{F(e^{j\theta})}{G(e^{j\theta})} - 1 \right) d\theta$$

which is Itakura-Saito divergence between the power-spectra of $F(e^{j\theta})$ and $G(e^{j\theta})$.

According to the properties of the β -divergence, IS-divergence has the same scale invariance when:

$$d_{IS}(\lambda x | \lambda y) = d_{IS}(x | y) \quad (1.17)$$

a consequence of this property is that the low energy parts of the signal p have the same relative importance as the high energy ones. This is the reason for which Itakura-Saito is very useful in the decomposition of audio signals, as they typically have a great dynamic range.

1.5 MM Type Algorithms

In statistics the most prevalent estimation methods, such as Maximum Likelihood (ML) and the Least Squares Method (LS), usually are intractable and cannot be solved analytically, so they are typically approximated through numerical methods. MM type algorithms are a recursive optimization method which is usually based in the convexity of the function to be minimized (or maximized)

1.5a Description

The basic principle of MM algorithms is the following: replace a difficult problem with one easier. In minimization problems the first M mean Majorize (we will define the term majorize later) and the second Minimize while in maximization problems then the first M means minorize (will also define it later) and the second maximize. This occurs with the following ways:

- avoiding big matrix inversions
- linearizing the initial problem
- separating the variables of the original problem
- gracefully addressing issues coming from inequalities
- conversion of non-differentiable problems to differentiable

The drawback of this process is increased recursion to achieve convergence.

Based on this we can say that MM is a generalization of EM (Expectation Maximization) type algorithms (or equivalently EM algorithms are a special case of the MM algorithms). To be able to use an EM algorithm we have to find a complete data space. In the E step of an EM algorithm the conditional with respect to the observed data, value of the logarithmic likelihood of the complete data. The replacement function produced by the E step is the minorizing function. In the M step this replacement function is maximized with respect to the parameters of the respective model.

Under this perspective maybe MM algorithm are easier to use as a complete data space does not need to be found. Careful consideration of the function of the logarithmic likelihood or some other objective function, with more attention given to convexity and inequalities.

1.5b Philosophy

Definition 1.5.1 Suppose $\theta^{(m)}$ corresponds to the constant value of the parameter θ and suppose $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ is a real function with respect to θ whose form is dependent on $\theta^{(m)}$. The function $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ is said to majorize a real function $f(\theta)$ at the point $\theta^{(m)}$ if:

$$g(\theta|\theta^{(m)}) \geq f(\theta), \quad \forall \theta \tag{1.18}$$

$$g(\theta^{(m)}|\theta^{(m)}) = f(\theta^{(m)}) \tag{1.19}$$

This definition explains that the surface of $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ is above the surface of $f(\theta)$ and that they only make contact when $\theta = \theta^{(m)}$. Inversely, $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ is said to minorize a real function $f(\theta)$ of $\theta^{(m)}$ if $-g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ majorizes $-f(\theta)$ at $\theta^{(m)}$.

Figure 1.10: Example of a Replacement/Helper Function

In an MM majorize-minimize type algorithm, we minimize $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ at the position $f(\theta)$. If the point $\theta^{(m+1)}$ is the minimizer of $g(\theta^{(m)}|\theta^{(m)})$, then we can show that the MM procedure forces $f(\theta)$ downhill:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(\theta^{(m+1)}) &= g(\theta^{(m+1)}|\theta^{(m)}) \\
 &\quad + f(\theta^{(m+1)}) - g(\theta^{(m+1)}|\theta^{(m)}) \\
 &\leq g(\theta^{(m)}|\theta^{(m)}) \\
 &\quad + f(\theta^{(m)}) - g(\theta^{(m)}|\theta^{(m)}) \\
 &= f(\theta^{(m)})
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.20}$$

This inequality is directly extracted from the fact that $g(\theta^{(m+1)}|\theta^{(m)}) \leq g(\theta^{(m)}|\theta^{(m)})$ and the definition 1.5.1. The property 1.20 gives MM algorithms a very good numerical stability. To maximize a real function $f(\theta)$, we minorize with a replacement function $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ and maximize $g(\theta|\theta^{(m)})$ so that we can find the next point $\theta^{(m+1)}$ for the next step.

Ways of Constructing a Replacement Function

A lot of majorize or minorize relationships can be extracted from various inequalities that stem from convexity or concavity. Here we will mention some of the important ones that will be used in the construction of the algorithm on the next chapter:

- (i) Jensen Inequality: suppose we have a random convex function $k(x)$ and any random variable X such that $k[E(X)] \leq E[k(X)]$. For the probability density functions $\alpha(x)$ and $\beta(x)$ and while $-\ln(x)$ is a convex function, it holds:

$$-\ln \left\{ E \left[\frac{\alpha(X)}{\beta(X)} \right] \right\} \leq -E \left[\ln \frac{\alpha(X)}{\beta(X)} \right]$$

If X has probability density $b(x)$ then the expected value $E[\alpha(X)/\beta(X)] = 1$, so :

$$E[\ln \alpha(X)] \leq E[\ln \beta(X)]$$

this inequality is what guarantees that the E step of (any) EM algorithm the minorizing function is constructed, making every EM algorithm a special case of the MM algorithm.

- (ii) Minimization through supporting hyperplanes: every linear function tangent to a convex function is a minimizer at the point of contact. So, if $k(\theta)$ is convex and differentiable

$$k(\theta) \geq k(\theta^{(m)}) + \nabla k(\theta^{(m)})^t (\theta - \theta^{(m)})$$

with the equality holding when $\theta = \theta^{(m)}$

- (iii) Maximization through the definition of Convexity : if we want to maximize a convex function, the we can use the definition of convexity. Suppose $k(t)$ is convex iff

$$k \left(\sum_i a_i t_i \right) \leq \sum_i a_i k(t_i)$$

for every collection of points t_i and their respective multipliers a_i , $a_i \geq 0$ and $\sum_i a_i = 1$. Application of the definition is particularly effective when composed with a linear function $x_T \theta$.

- (iv) Maximization through a square upper bound : if a convex function $k(\theta)$ is twice differentiable and has bound curvature, then we can maximize it with a second order equation with big enough curvature and tangent $k(\theta)$ at $\theta^{(m)}$. In

algebraic terms, if we can find a positive definite matrix M such that $M - \nabla^2 k(\theta)$ nonnegative defined for every θ , then

$$k(\theta) \leq k(\theta^{(m)}) + \nabla k(\theta^{(m)})^t (\theta - \theta^{(m)}) + \frac{1}{2} (\theta - \theta^{(m)})^T M (\theta - \theta^{(m)})$$

provides a squared upper bound.

- (v) The inequality of arithmetic-geometric mean : a special case of the definition of convexity. If we set $k(t) = e^t$ and $a_i = 1/m$, then

$$e^{\left(\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m t_i\right)} \leq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m e^{t_i}$$

and if we set $x_i = e^{t_i}$ then we get the inequality of the arithmetic-geometric mean

$$\sqrt[m]{\prod_{i=1}^m x_i} \leq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i$$

- (vi) Cauchy-Schwartz Inequality: The inequality for the Euclidean norm is a special case of the minimization through support hyperplanes, The function $k(\theta) = \|\theta\|$ is convex because it satisfies the triangular inequality and the condition $\|a\theta\| = |a| \cdot \|\theta\|$. Αφού $k(\theta) = \sqrt{\sum_i \theta_i^2}$, $\nabla k(\theta) = \theta/\|\theta\|$, so the inequality of the minimization through support hyperplanes becomes:

$$\|\theta\| \geq \|\theta^{(m)}\| + \frac{(\theta - \theta^{(m)})^t \theta^{(m)} \theta^{(m)}}{\|\theta^{(m)}\|} = \frac{\theta^t \theta^{(m)}}{\|\theta^{(m)}\|}$$

which is the Cauchy-Schwartz inequality.

Convergence

A typical MM algorithm has linear rate of convergence:

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|\theta^{(m+1)} - \theta^*\|}{\|\theta^{(m)} - \theta^*\|} = 1$$

in contrast to the Newton-Raphson algorithm, which has square rate of convergence newer a local optimum point and, as a consequence, has a lot faster convergence with fewer iterations :

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\|\theta^{(m+1)} - \theta^*\|}{\|\theta^{(m)} - \theta^*\|^2} = c > 1$$

Though if we look more carefully a iteration of N-R algorithm of the form:

$$\theta^{(m)} = \theta^{(m)} - \nabla^2 f(\theta^{(m)})^{-1} \nabla f(\theta^{(m)})$$

we see that it requires the calculation and inversion of the Hessian matrix. If θ has p elements, then the calculations to invert $p \times p$ Hessian matrix are close to p^3 . Contrary to the MM algorithm where we separate the parameters and usually needs p or p^2 numerical calculations per iteration.

So, well formed MM algorithms need more iterations but fewer numerical calculations per iteration than Newton-Raphson. Generalizing, often MM algorithms are difficult to be outperformed as far as their numerical stability and simplicity is concerned.

Chapter 2

Extracting the Algorithm

In this chapter we will present the structure of the data input of the algorithm and we will extract step by step the nonnegative matrix factorization MM algorithm. The process for the selection of the kernel, the prior distribution in order to achieve smooth transition on the rows of H , we will find the minimization criteria and will extract the step of the algorithm that gives the renewal of each row h_k . Finally, we will present the performance indicators we will use to evaluate the algorithm's performance. We have to note here that the following chapter is a complete analysis of [7].

2.1 Kernel Selection and Minimization Criteria

As prior knowledge we will suppose Markov chains with respect to the rows of H , preferring in this way smoothness among them and based on the fact that the rows of H are the spectra activators, we enforce a smooth transition from one to the next, thus not allowing temporal discontinuities (or sudden gaps). No model is supposed for the columns of W , even though the structure imposed on the rows of H could easily be used for the columns of W . Furthermore, a completely different structure (or model) could be supposed W .

Returning to extracting the algorithm, suppose

$$p(\mathbf{H}) = \prod_{k=1}^K \prod_{n=2}^N p(h_{kn}|h_{k(n-1)})p(h_{k1}) \quad (2.1)$$

where $p(h_{kn}|h_{k(n-1)})$ is a probability density function with the most probable value being $h_{k(n-1)}$. The reason we choose this way of modeling, is to limit h_{kn} so that it will not differ significantly from $h_{k(n-1)}$. Given that the physical signals do not have

abrupt changes, it extremely improbable that in a natural signal from on window to the next, given the sampling frequency is 44.1KHz and the temporal distance between samples 0,000023sec. This constraint forces the algorithm to keep stability in the rows of H (the matrix of the temporal activators) since in every iteration every elements value is dependent on its previous (with respect to time) value.

A possible selection of probability density function is the inverse Gamma:

$$IG(h_{hk}|\alpha, (\alpha + 1)h_{k(n-1)}) = ((\alpha + 1)h_{k(n-1)})^\alpha \cdot h_{kn}^{-(\alpha+1)} \cdot e^{-((\alpha+1)h_{k(n-1)}/h_{kn})} \cdot \Gamma(\alpha) \quad (2.2)$$

with $h_{kn} \geq 0$ [5]. Selecting a high value for the parameter α mitigates the distribution giving it specific mode for the point h_{kn} . We have the probability function of h_{kn} given $h_{k(n-1)}$:

$$p(h_{kn}|h_{k(n-1)}) = IG(h_{kn}|h_{k(n-1)}|\alpha, (\alpha + 1)h_{k(n-1)}) \quad (2.3)$$

Searching the MAP estimator through the minimization of the function :

$$C_1 = -\log p(W, H|V) \quad (2.4)$$

$$= D_{IS}(V|WH) - \log p(H) - \log p(W) \quad (2.5)$$

$$= D_{IS}(V|WH) + \frac{1}{\alpha + 1} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{n=2}^N d_{IS}(h_{k(n-1)}|h_{kn}) + \log h_{k(n-1)} + cst(\tilde{h})^1 \quad (2.6)$$

equality holds for up to constant terms

Reformulating the problem to minimize,

$$C_1(W, H) = D_{IS}(V|WH) + (\alpha + 1)P_1(H) \quad (2.7)$$

$$P_1(H) = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{n=1}^N d_{IS}(h_{k(n-1)}|h_{kn}) + \frac{\log h_{k(n-1)}}{\alpha + 1} + cst(\tilde{h}) \quad (2.8)$$

we find tha because of teh term $\log h_{k(n-1)}$ the problem is ill posed, because $\forall W, H$ and a nonnegative matrix D_1 with coefficients c_k then the minimizing function becomes :

$$C_1(WD_1, DH) = C_1(W, H) + (N - 1) \sum_k \log c_k \quad (2.9)$$

so when it reaches a marginal situation $D_1 \rightarrow 0$, then the matrix $\hat{H} \rightarrow 0$ and $\hat{W} \rightarrow \infty$.

On simple and easily applicable solution, without, changing the objective function is to delete this term ($\log h_{k(n-1)}$) :

$$P_2(H) = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{n=1}^N d_{IS}(h_{k(n-1)}|h_{kn}) \quad (2.10)$$

which penalizes big divergences from the $h_{k(n-1)}$ column to the h_{kn} column. in doing that, we lose statistical meaning of the regularization term, but we gain an well-posed problem. The objective function is defined as:

$$C_2(W, H) = D_{IS}(V|WH) + \lambda * P_2(H) \quad (2.11)$$

As long as we have defined the regularized objective function and having checked the that the problem is well defined, we go on to the extraction of the MM algorithm.

2.2 The MM Algorithm

The problem now is formed as the finding the solution to the previous equation,

$$C(W, H) = D_{IS}(V|WH) + \lambda * P_2(H) \quad (2.12)$$

first, we will find the algorithms step when $\lambda = 0$ and afterwards we will find the step for $\lambda > 0$.

2.2a $\lambda = 0$

In the case where $\lambda = 0$ the function that has to be minimized is:

$$\min_{\mathbf{H}} C(\mathbf{H}) = D(\mathbf{V}|\mathbf{WH}) \quad \mu \varepsilon \mathbf{H} \geq 0 \quad (2.13)$$

with the matrix \mathbf{W} as constant. The objective function $C(\mathbf{H})$ splits in $\sum_n D(\mathbf{v}_n|\mathbf{Wh}_n)$, where \mathbf{v}_n and \mathbf{h}_n is the n -th row of \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{H} respectively, so the problem that remains to be solved is:

$$\min_{\mathbf{h}} C(\mathbf{h}) = D_{IS}(\mathbf{v}|\mathbf{Wh}) \quad \mu \varepsilon \mathbf{h} \geq 0 \quad (2.14)$$

where $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}_+^F$, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{F \times K}$, $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}_+^K$. Where \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{h} are the columns of the matrices V and H respectively.

but we know from (1.6) that :

$$D_{IS}(\mathbf{v}|\mathbf{Wh}) = \sum_{f=1}^F \sum_{n=1}^N d_{IS}([\mathbf{v}]_{fn}|[\mathbf{Wh}]_{fn}) \quad (2.15)$$

but as we said at (1.14), every divergence in the class Bregman Divergences (such as Itakura-Saito) can be analyzed in the convex, concave and constant part, as follows :

$$d_{IS}(x|y) = \check{d}_{IS}(x|y) + \hat{d}_{IS}(x|y) + \bar{d}_{IS}(x)$$

Also at [7] the following function has been proposed and proven as a replacement function $C(\mathbf{h}) = \sum_f C_f(\mathbf{h}) = \sum_f d(v_f|[\mathbf{Wh}]_f)$:

$$G(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \sum_f \left[\sum_k \frac{w_{fk} \tilde{h}_k}{\tilde{v}_f} \check{d} \left(v_f | \tilde{v}_f \frac{h_k}{\tilde{h}_k} \right) \right] + \left[\hat{d}'(v_f|\tilde{v}_f) \sum_k w_{fk} (h_k - \tilde{h}_k) + \hat{d}(v_f|\tilde{v}_f) \right] + \bar{d}(v_f) \quad (2.16)$$

with

$$\check{d}_{IS}(x|y) = xy^{-1} \quad (2.17)$$

$$\hat{d}_{IS}(x|y) = \log y \quad (2.18)$$

$$\bar{d}_{IS}(x) = x(\log x - 1) \quad (2.19)$$

where :

$$\check{G}_f(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \sum_k \frac{w_{fk}\tilde{h}_k}{\tilde{v}_f} \check{d}\left(v_f|\tilde{v}_f \frac{h_k}{\tilde{h}_k}\right) \quad (2.20)$$

\check{G}_f is the convex part of G that can be proven through Jensen inequality, because if its convexity $\check{d}(x|y)$ it will be $\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\mathbf{h}) = \check{C}_f(\mathbf{h})$ such as the fact that $\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) \geq \check{C}_f(\mathbf{h})$ and as a consequence it will be the replacement function for the concave part of C ,

$$\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \hat{C}(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) + \nabla^T \hat{C}_f(\tilde{\mathbf{h}})(\mathbf{h} - \tilde{\mathbf{h}}) \quad (2.21)$$

$$\mu \varepsilon \nabla_{h_k} \hat{C}_f(\mathbf{h}) = w_{fk} \hat{d}'(v_f | [\mathbf{W}\mathbf{h}]_f) \quad (2.22)$$

and \hat{G} is the concave part and the first degree Taylor approximation C_f . So the function is valid $\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\mathbf{h}) = \hat{C}_f(\mathbf{h})$ as well as the fact that $\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) \geq \hat{C}_f(\mathbf{h})$ since the tangent in any point is the upper bound of a concave function. Adding $\check{G}(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}})$, $\hat{G}(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}})$ and $\bar{d}(v_f)$ we get the replacement function. Reminding that with \mathbf{h} we refer to the columns of H we can rewrite (2.16) as follows:

$$G_k(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \sum_k G_k(h_k|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) + cst(\tilde{h}) \quad (2.23)$$

$$G_k(h_k|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = h_k \left[\sum_f \frac{w_{fk}}{\tilde{v}_f} \hat{d}\left(v_f|\tilde{v}_f \frac{h_k}{\tilde{h}_k}\right) \right] + h_k \left[\sum_f w_{fk} \hat{d}'(v_f|\tilde{v}_f) \right] \quad (2.24)$$

replacing these: $\check{d}(x|y)$ and $\hat{d}(x|y)$ at (2.24) we get :

$$G_k(h_k|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \frac{\tilde{h}_k^2}{h_k} \left(\sum_f w_{fk} \frac{v_f}{\tilde{v}_f^2} \right) + h_k \left(\sum_f \frac{w_{fk}}{\tilde{v}_f} \right) + cst(\tilde{h}) \quad (2.25)$$

where $cst(\tilde{h})$ are constant terms with respect to \mathbf{h} . Differentiating G with respect to h_k we get :

$$\nabla_{h_k} G_k(h_k|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \left(\sum_f \frac{w_{fk}}{\tilde{v}_f} \right) - \frac{\tilde{h}_k^2}{h_k^2} \left(\sum_f w_{fk} \frac{v_f}{\tilde{v}_f^2} \right) \quad (2.26)$$

We now can minimize $C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}})$ by minimizing in its place $G(\mathbf{h}|\tilde{\mathbf{h}})$. It's derivative $C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}})$ can be written as the difference of two nonnegative functions such that :

$$\nabla_{h_k} C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \nabla_{h_k}^+ C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) - \nabla_{h_k}^- C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) \quad (2.27)$$

$$\nabla_{h_k}^+ C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1} \quad (2.28)$$

$$\nabla_{h_k}^- C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}}) = \sum_f w_{fk} v_f \tilde{v}_f^{-2} \quad (2.29)$$

so the step of h_k equals :

$$h_k = \tilde{h}_k \sqrt{\frac{\nabla_{h_k}^- C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}})}{\nabla_{h_k}^+ C(\tilde{\mathbf{h}})}} \quad (2.30)$$

$$h_k = \tilde{h}_k \sqrt{\frac{\sum_f w_{fk} v_f \tilde{v}_f^{-2}}{\sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1}}} \quad (2.31)$$

2.2b $\lambda > 0$

Adding the regularization term at

$$C_2(W, H) = D_{IS}(V|WH) + \lambda * P_2(H)$$

we can reformulate the problem as follows:

$$C_P(\mathbf{h}_n) = D_{IS}(\mathbf{v}_n|W\mathbf{h}_n) + L(\mathbf{h}_n; \mathbf{h}_{n-1}, \mathbf{h}_{n+1}) \quad (2.32)$$

$$L(\mathbf{h}_n; \mathbf{h}_{n-1}, \mathbf{h}_{n+1}) = \lambda \sum_k d(\mathbf{h}_{k(n-1)}|\mathbf{h}_{kn}) + d(\mathbf{h}_{kn}|\mathbf{h}_{k(n+1)}) \quad (2.33)$$

For this problem it is easy to find a replacement function

$$C_P(\mathbf{h}_n) = G(\mathbf{h}_n|\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_n) + L(\mathbf{h}_n; \mathbf{h}_{n-1}, \mathbf{h}_{n+1}) \quad (2.34)$$

where again it is split in functions of its variables and the minimization takes us to the next step:

$$h_{kn} = \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{h}_{kn}^2 \sum_f w_{fk} v_f \tilde{v}_f^{-2} + \lambda h_{k(n-1)}}{\sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1} + \lambda h_{k(n+1)}^{-1}}} \quad (2.35)$$

this relationship is valid only for $n = 2, \dots, N-1$, in the extreme cases (at the two ends of the markov chain) the update of h_{kn} is given by :

$$h_{k1} = \frac{\sqrt{\lambda^2 - 4(\sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1} + \lambda/h_{k2})(-\sum_f w_{fk} v_f \tilde{v}_f^{-2} + \lambda/h_{k2})} + \lambda}{2 \sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1} + \lambda/h_{k2}} \quad (2.36)$$

$$h_{kN} = \frac{\sqrt{\lambda^2 - 4 * (\sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1})(-\sum_f w_{fk} v_f \tilde{v}_f^{-2}) h_{kN}^2 + \lambda h_{k(N-1)} - \lambda}}{2 \sum_f w_{fk} \tilde{v}_f^{-1}} \quad (2.37)$$

Finally we have to mention the the computational complexity of the algorithm ranges around $O(FKN)$.

Figure 2.1: (right) NMF algorithm and (left) the algorithms flowchart.

Part II

Methodology & Conclusions

Chapter 3

Measurements and Results

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter analysis of the nonnegative matrix factorization with the Itakura Saito objective function algorithm on monaural drum sound sources will be presented. The logic behind the steps taken during this analysis will be explained and the algorithm's performance will be evaluated with the use of performance indicators that we will describe in the next paragraph.

To evaluate the performance of the algorithm, two signals were manufactured (which are shown at figures 3.14 and 3.15) composed of synthetic drum sounds from commercial drum libraries with a time span around 35 seconds. This concept was followed in order to preserve each source completely separated and independent from every other thus keeping the performance analysis as accurate as possible. Moreover, a substantial attempt was made to keep the realism of the performed rhythms to a high level, applying varied dynamics at all parts of the performance. For example, ghost notes up to fortissimo hits that clip the signal on the snare drum were used in order to evaluate the algorithm in as realistic situations as possible.

The structure of the first signal is as follows, a relatively fast paces rhythm of 16ths at a tempo of around 100bpm, a usual rhythm in popular music genres such as Funk, Rock 'n' Roll, Bebop and dense enough to check whether often repeated parts in a signal persist on (or 'polute') more output signals than less often repeated temporal patterns or frequencies (or both). More specifically, the Hihat is repeated 16 times per meter in comparison to the snare drum that is repeated two or three times per meter or the Crash that is repeated once in four meters.

Figure 3.1: The first signal in the time and frequency domain

Figure 3.2: The second signal in the time and frequency domain

The second signal is again at the tempo of 100bpm but on 8 beat rhythm, usually used in more commercial musical genres, to examine the algorithm's performance if larger temporal distances exist between identical repeated spectral patterns (eg. hits of the snare drum), if the separation impacts negatively the separated sources when it has to deal with the sharp attack of the snare when coming from a relatively quieter time frame or if because of low energy noise the algorithm's point of convergence changes.

The basic parameters that affect the algorithms performance and will be checked are;

- The amount of iterations required to converge, when the difference of the value of the Itakura Saito distance from previous iteration is small enough
- The possible value of the regularization value λ that is required in order to preserve the attack of each percussion instrument, given that they are sharp, and at the same time to avoid overfitting, where by achieving numerically greater precision "incontinuities" are introduced on the perceptive end of the separation.
- Window size, in order to find the best balance between information in the frequency domain and the loss of information in the frequency domain.
- Finally, it will be evaluated how many Components are ideal to perform factorization in order to get the most meaningful and detailed outputs.

3.2 Performance indicators

In this part of the chapter the performance indicators that will be used will be analyzed to evaluate the performance of the algorithm that was developed on the previous part of the chapter. The indicators mentioned come from different sources and are not necessarily used in systems like the one we have described so far.

3.2a Source Separation Performance Criteria

Blind Source Separation technique is one more tool to separate and perform noise removal on audio signals, based on statistical characteristics of the observed signals. In [18] several objective criteria to evaluate the performance have been formed, easily applicable to a variety of situations, including this one.

The basic principle of these objective performance evaluation criteria is the analysis of the output signal $out[n]$ in to partial signals, like :

$$out = s_{target} + e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif} \quad (3.1)$$

The signal s_{target} is the initial signal which is being approximated and $e_{interf}, e_{noise}, e_{artif}$ are fault signals caused by interference, noise and artifacts through processing respectively. This analysis is based in the orthogonal projection technique. The most important advantage of this particular way of analysis is that it makes no presupposition on the way the initial

Figure 3.3: (above) The spectra of the first signal before insertion to the algorithm, (left) the initial sources, (right) the algorithms estimations, (below) the estimated signal

Figure 3.4: ((above) The spectra of the first signal before insertion to the algorithm, (left) the initial sources, (right) the algorithms estimations, (below) the estimated signal

signal was separated and can be used, as mentioned before, in a wide spectrum of algorithms and applications.

Having analyzed the output signal as if equation (3.1), the following criteria can be defined:

$$SAR = 10 \log \frac{\|s_{target} + e_{interf} + e_{noise}\|^2}{\|e_{artif}\|^2} \quad (3.2)$$

$$SDR = 10 \log \frac{\|s_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{interf} + e_{noise} + e_{artif}\|^2} \quad (3.3)$$

$$SIR = 10 \log \frac{\|s_{target}\|^2}{\|e_{inter}\|^2} \quad (3.4)$$

all the above are implemented through the BSSEval Toolbox [18] in Matlab.

3.3 Searching the Optimum Parameter Set

3.3a Initial Measurements

Initially the necessary iterations the algorithm requires for convergence, independently of the rest of the parameters, will be assessed, to find out how many iterations are required so that the i^{th} iteration does not differ numerically (and intuitively) from the $i^{th} - 1$. In this way and while the algorithm therefore converges after a fixed number of iterations, we will check with this number the rest parameters from the parameter set.

After about 50 test runs on both signals it was discovered that the algorithm seems to be converging just before 1,000 iterations (something shown in the figure 3.5). We have to note here that tests were made not only on 1,000, but on 2,500, 5,000 and 10,000. On every test the algorithm demonstrated the same behavior as far as convergence is concerned, above 1,000 iterations the difference between consecutive iterations was small and decreasing but slowly, where the weight of increasing accuracy is less than the computational cost. One downside of iterating more times and thus keeping on minimizing the objective function is overfitting. The algorithm attempts to fit its prediction on the signal more than required and as a consequence the prediction loses its perceivable temporal continuity, as there are obvious temporal gaps .

The λ parameter plays an important role, something shown in figure 3.5, while convergence with a bigger value of λ seems to be numerically worse (the more the λ increases the worse it is), something that comes as a result of the enforced temporal continuity on the lines of H and not due to the worse quality of the estimated signal.

Figure 3.5: 48 initial measurements to check speed of convergence

Complexity and Time of Execution

Generally the computational complexity of the algorithm is $O(FKN)$

The correspondence is as follows, F represents half plus one of the DFT points, K is the number of the required components and N is the amount of the activators on the lines of H . The time required to execute 1000 iterations is around 300 seconds for a file of around 30 seconds, 10 components and the size of the FFT is 2048 samples on a Inter Core2Quad 6600 processor.

3.3b Searching the optimum λ

Moving further on searching the optimum λ , several values were tested, starting from 5 up to 20 but it immediately apparent that for $\lambda < 10$ from the results, while the objective function converged to better values faster, the output signals from the algorithm were mostly wrongfully. The algorithm behaved the same way when more than ten components were used, more output signals were similar to floor noise. When $\lambda = 20$, failure to perform separation was usual, even though the perceivable result was better. For the values of $\lambda < 10$

Figure 3.6: The signals/components as extracted from the algorithm (before the grouping stage) on the frequency domain

Figure 3.7: The signals/components as extracted from the algorithm (before the grouping stage) on the time domain

and $\lambda = 20$ we unfortunately did not keep the measurements because the rate of failure of separation made an objective evaluation prohibitive.

For these reasons it was decided to search an optimum value of lambda within the interval $10 \geq \lambda \geq 17$. In this interval two things have to be taken into consideration, keep the signal's perceivable quality at acceptable levels and the value of the cost function has to remain small. An interesting observation is that with bigger values of λ the objective function did not numerically achieve the levels that it did with smaller values of λ but the acoustically perceivable result of higher values of λ was qualitatively superior. Each signal went through the algorithm four times (procedure which is valid for every step of the evaluation process) for every value of λ and then we calculated the average of the set of results.

According to the measurements (as seen on the figures 3.8 and 3.9) the most consistent behavior was for $\lambda = 12$ which was chosen. For $\lambda = 14$ & 17, qualitatively were better but the algorithm's behavior under these parameters was less predictable, which is the reason the measurements are inconsistent.

3.3c Searching for the optimum window size

The initial parameter settings that were set for the window size was 1024 samples on a sampling frequency of 44100Hz which corresponds to $\frac{1024}{44100} = 25\text{ms}$, when on a pretty unusual case a 32nd on a tempo of 240bpm is approximately equal to 31.25ms, so the window size of 1024 samples seems to be sufficient as far as its temporal adequacy is concerned. For a bigger percentage of music a window size of 4096 samples would be sufficient as it corresponds to $\frac{4096}{44100} = 92\text{ms}$, while 16ths on a tempo of 120bpm, one of the more usual tempo values in the industry, correspond to approximately to 125 ms. For this reason we will test window sizes that are 1024, 2048, 4096 and 8192 samples large.

As it seems on the measurements (on figures 3.10 and 3.11) the differences of the results among the window sizes are small. A failure to perform separation on the first signal's Crash and Hihat components is apparent when the window size is 1024 samples (on three of the four tests). On both signals the window size of 2048 samples seems to provide adequate frequency information to perform correct and more consistent separation.

3.3d Searching the optimum number of components

Initially the component parameter was set to 10 components as it was mentioned from literature as a balanced number of components to separate musical signals but it was now known if this number was relevant to perform separation on 4 sources or whether better and more accurate separation could be performed with more or even with less components. As a result of this process separation on 4 components (trying to match one output signal to one source), and 5, 10 and 20

From the measurements (on figures 3.12 and 3.13) it is apparent that a one by one correspondence cannot easily occur, as a low energy component in the music (such as floor

(a) SAR

(b) SIR

(c) SDR

Figure 3.8: Results for the optimum value of λ on the first signal

Figure 3.9: Results for the optimum value of λ on the second signal

(a) SAR

(b) SIR

(c) SDR

Figure 3.10: Results for the optimum window size on the first signal

Figure 3.11: Results for the optimum window size on the first signal

(a) SAR

(b) SIR

(c) SDR

Figure 3.12: Measurements for the optimum number of components on the first signal

or current noise) can take over an output signal and not one of the desired sources, this is due to the selected objective function, as it 'perceives' as equal low and high energy signals.

Separation in 5 components brings back better results, but it has the most inconsistent behavior, either the algorithm will get the correct separation of the four sources and one signal consisted of low energy noise or it completely fails, as usually in the second signal where the Crash source was not found correctly and parts of it were mixed with the rest of the signals on two out of the four measurements.

When the number of the components is increased to 10, we observe the expected behavior, relatively well and consistent source separation. The separation correct most of the times but not as good as with 20 components. This is perceivable on an acoustical level. The results with 20 components have more details from the initial sources, but that occurs because most output signals are of low energy which may contain only one percussive hit or only a very small subset of frequencies. The first fact alone makes a difficult case of regrouping the output signals as they do not contain a lot of information.

(a) SAR

(b) SIR

(c) SDR

Figure 3.13: Measurements for the optimum number of components on the second signal

Figure 3.14: Estimations of the sources from the first signal as they were output from the algorithm after they were grouped compared to the initial midi and represented from the waveforms (on the even lines). The black dots (on the odd lines) represent the sample activations from the library of synthetic drums.

Figure 3.15: Estimations of the sources from the second signal as they were output from the algorithm after they were grouped compared to the initial midi and represented from the waveforms (on the even lines). The black dots (on the odd lines) represent the sample activations from the library of synthetic drums.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

4.1 Conclusions

Purpose of this thesis was the study of the application of nonnegative matrix factorization on monophonic audio sources consisted of percussive (drum) sources with the purpose of separation. Blind source separation applied to monophonic source separation more generally forms a under-determined problem, while the sources (unknowns) we want to extract are more than the signal (equation) we have as input. The properties of the sources were used in this thesis is nonnegativity and the smooth transition of the amplitude on consecutive temporal points.

In chapter 2 the method under which the input signal is transformed with the Discrete Fourier Transform and imported to the algorithm for processing. Next, a historical overview of matrix factorization was made, a comparison of the was Nonnegative matrix factorization separates the data comparatively to other methods with an intuitive way. Afterwards Itakura-Saito (IS) was described from the β divergence family making obvious its relationship with the euclidean distance and relative entropy (KL divergence), but more basically, its relationship with acoustical signals, the fact that it comes out naturally that it is a distance between two power spectra. Finally, a description of the philosophy behind Majorize Minimize (or Minimize Maximize) and some ways of producing them, such as the creation of a replacement (helper) function.

Having made the groundwork, in chapter 3, with the use of I-S minimizing objective function (or cost function) and an additional constraint the smoothness on the lines of H with the use of a Markov chain, the algorithm was extracted. The result was the extraction of an unsupervised source separation algorithm, where all the sources represent (non negative) parts of the full spectrum.

According to the measurements of chapter 4, the existing algorithm succeeds in a great extent its target regarding the recognition of the correct temporal activators, the lines of H , even if the value of the regularization parameter λ is critical as the result is dependent on the signal's content as far as their temporal placement and length is concerned. Next, we

will separate the results in two basic orientations:

4.1a Audio Quality Oriented

When the expected output signal extracted from the algorithm, has large temporal duration (for example a Ride or Crash) then the values of λ need to be larger in order to avoid sharp differences of the values on the rows of H favoring smoothness over overfitting, on the acoustical (perceptive) level avoiding abrupt cuts of cymbal's tail.

Selecting a large value of the regularization parameter λ has an impact on the timbre of the separated percussive sounds compared to the initial sources that are activated at approximately the same time. It prevents separation from approximating the sources that make up the input signal. One usual behavior of the algorithm during the evaluation phase was mixing the timbre of the activated cymbal with the timbre of the snare drum, when both of them were activated at the same time while, at the same time, other "parts" of the cymbal's ADSR phase were split into different components, allowing a relatively accurate separation from the rest percussive elements of the input signal.

Increasing the number of components, during the evaluation phase we observed what was already noted in the literature. The number of 10 components appears to be a golden section between correct separation and amount of information on each component. Increasing the component number to 15 or 20 separation into parts usually containing extreme low energy noise or parts of sources of close to zero amplitude or a small fraction of frequencies from a specific source. In each one of the precious cases separation becomes very difficult. According to the measurements, the increased complexity introduced by the higher number of components does not return analogous benefits in the quality of separation in the case of many percussive instruments. Choosing to increase the number of components to a number larger than 10 would make possible the analysis of one and only one percussive instrument on the different complex timbres it possibly creates.

4.1b Significance Oriented

When the importance is based not on the re-use of the sound material to further mix but use it in order to understand information that are possibly contained in the material, such as the number of percussive instruments or the activation times of each percussive instrument in the input signal, one application being transcription, increasing the value of the λ parameter seems to have a negative impact to the algorithm's performance, while it (the algorithm) in its attempt to avoid overfitting mixes different percussive elements contained in the signal together, decreasing the dimensionality of the initial signal's spectrum (which is the (which is the algorithms benchmark) even more wrongfully, combining two percussion instruments.

The total number of components could play an important role as percussion are well separated a lot more frequently, and that actually reveals again the need for a method to recognize categorize and group the output signals, which if implemented correctly it would

positively affect this stage making measurements even better without significantly affecting their use for recognition of the initial signal.

Window size parameter on both signals gave the best results when set at 2048 samples, a fact that seems counter intuitive at first, but based on the fact that there has been supposed no model for the spectra on the columns of W , they could have energy in only one frequency bin, something not usually found in naturally created sounds. In comparison to the columns of W , this algorithm succeeds in its purpose to create a reliable way to produce temporal activators for percussive spectra, without this meaning it can successfully converge reliably on the correct spectra.

4.2 Future Work

One of the most important strengths of this algorithm and at the same time its biggest weakness is the freedom on the columns of W . While this freedom allows the application of activation recognitions (the elements on the lines of H) on a spectrogram of any type of signal, either a natural instrument or an artificially constructed signal (with purposes other than music), it does not allow NMF to regain the expected spectrograms.

Initial tests, with biased static spectra (omitting the algorithm's update on the W matrix), have shown that the algorithm attains with a higher precision the (approximately) correct values on the rows of H . This suggests that with a more informed model of spectra template predictions, it should be possible to model the smoothness to precision the correct number of components and the validity of activations, which translates to the columns of W and the lines of H respectively.

Some possible direction to research towards this can be:

- Enforcing smoothness on the predicted values of the columns of W , or, in other words, use of the smoothness modeling H on W .
- Partial training of W in order to expect the spectra of one specific type of percussion for each sound and limit the effect of the update steps in order to contain deviations from that training.
- To treat each FFT block as a probability density function (pdf) and approximate it with a semi random sampling method (e.g. MCMC) or fit the pdfs with a (customized) EM.
- Partial training of the activation times causing the Markov chain on the rows of H in order to guide the algorithm into more accurate spectra estimation.

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